

Supplementary Material

Utilization of Agro-Waste in Eco-Friendly Composites Based on Pineapple, Taro, and Banana Fibre

Abstract

This review explores the potential of using pineapple leaf fibre (PALF), taro fibre, and banana fibre as eco-friendly reinforcements in natural fibre-reinforced polymer composites. Based on the contemporary literature, the study emphasizes the physicochemical characteristics, surface modifications, and mechanical properties of these agrowaste-derived fibres. PALF and banana fibres exhibit robust mechanical characteristics and reveal excellent compatibility with thermoplastic and thermoset matrices. These attributes render them appropriate for lightweight structural applications. Taro fibre, while not extensively researched, demonstrates moderate strength and high biodegradability, thereby rendering it a viable candidate for disposable and packaging applications. Each fibre has distinct advantage, as shown by the fact that taro fibre improves biodegradability, banana fibre combines strength and flexibility, and PALF adds rigidity. Surface treatments like alkali and silane significantly enhance fibre-matrix adhesion and contribute to the durability of the composites. From an environmental standpoint, these fibres support circular-economy principles, reduce reliance on synthetic materials, and help rural agricultural communities. This review fills a significant research void by providing a comparative analysis of these fibres and acts as a valuable resource for material selection in the production of sustainable composites.

Keywords: Agro-waste, pineapple fibre, banana fibre, taro fibre, composites, eco-friendly

2. Natural Fibre Composites

Natural fibre composites can be manufactured using several techniques, including hand lay-up, compression molding, injection molding, RTM, and pultrusion [60]. Each process has distinct advantages contingent on the application, production volume, and the required qualities of the finished product. The hand lay-up method is a simple and economical process in which fibre layers are manually placed into a mold, followed by the application of resin [61, 62]. One of the main benefits of this process is that it allows manual control over fibre orientation and enables alignment of fibres along specific load directions or design requirements. The method is particularly suitable for small-scale or prototype production since it requires minimal equipment and investment. Nevertheless, the process can be labour-intensive, and the final quality often depends on operator skill, leading to variations between batches. Compression

molding and injection molding are advanced fabrication techniques used when higher throughput and consistent material quality are required. In compression molding, fibre mats or chopped fibres are placed into a heated mold and pressed to cure the resin, ensuring uniform load distribution and a fully impregnated matrix. Injection molding, by contrast, involves combining chopped fibres with resin, which is then injected into a heated mold under pressure. This technique supports uniform fibre dispersion and the production of complex geometries with high repeatability. Nonetheless, the turbulent flow during injection generally leads to random fibre orientation and reduced fibre length, limiting the degree of control over fibre alignment. RTM involves injecting a fluid resin into a template filled with dry fibre preforms, whereas pultrusion is used for the continuous production of composite rods, sheets, and profiles [63]. The selection of the processing method influences various aspects, including fibre orientation, fibre length, void content, and the overall homogeneity of the composite, ultimately affecting its mechanical properties. Table S2 elucidates the standard techniques for composite fabrication, derived from various investigations.

The lightweight nature of natural fibre composites makes them particularly appealing for applications in aviation and automotive industries, where weight reduction is a critical factor [6]. With a favorable strength-to-weight ratio, they offer the required strength for many applications without adding significant weight [64]. These composites are esteemed for their acoustic and thermal insulation capabilities, which are advantageous for car panels, construction materials, and consumer products [65]. Nonetheless, despite these benefits, natural fibre composites have certain limitations. A primary concern is their capacity for moisture absorption, which can lead to swelling, dimensional instability, and a decline in mechanical properties over time. Elevated moisture levels in natural fibres can undermine fibre-matrix contact, leading to delamination or cracking. Consequently, moisture-resistant treatments and the application of hydrophobic matrix elements are frequently essential to enhance the endurance of composites.

A further constraint is the inconsistency in the characteristics of natural fibres. The strength, stiffness, and overall performance of natural fibres can vary considerably depending on the source plant, climatic conditions, and fibre extraction techniques. These inconsistencies in properties, caused by heterogeneity, can create challenges for ensuring quality control and achieving standardized production. Furthermore, natural fibres tend to be more combustible than synthetic fibres, making fire resistance a critical factor in specific applications. Initiatives to improve flame suppression involve the application of fire-resistant chemicals or the creation

of hybrid composites that integrate natural fibres with synthetic, non-combustible components [66].

Notwithstanding these limitations, natural fibre composites are increasingly used across diverse industries. In the automotive industry, they are used for lightweight components such as door panels, dashboards, and interior trims, where weight reduction can enhance fuel efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The construction sector employs natural fibre composites for partition boards, insulation panels, and composite decking, owing to their insulating properties and sustainable, environmentally friendly attributes. Natural fibre composites also serve the packaging sector by providing biodegradable replacements for plastic, particularly in single-use containers. In the retail goods sector, these resources are used in products such as furniture, footwear, and sporting goods, where their visual appeal and environmental attributes are highly valued. Therefore, it can be said that natural fibre-reinforced polymer composites have considerable promise for sustainable development across multiple sectors. Their intrinsic environmental advantages, along with their advantageous mechanical characteristics and lightweight nature, render them formidable contenders for diverse applications. Although natural fibre composites have significant potential, problems such as moisture retention, fibre-matrix adhesion, and material variability persist. These issues necessitate further research into surface treatments, hybrid composites, and processing methods to fully capitalize on their commercial value.

3.3. Surface treatment and fibre modification

Similar to other natural fibres, PALF requires surface modification to enhance bonding with hydrophobic polymer matrices. Insufficient interfacial adhesion often leads to voids, fibre pull-out, and reduced mechanical properties. Various physical and chemical surface treatment techniques address this constraint [24].

Alkali treatment, also known as mercerization, is the primary method and involves soaking fibres in a sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution (usually 5–10%) for a specific time [36]. By removing lignin, hemicellulose, and waxy residues, this treatment increases surface roughness, facilitates fibril separation, and ultimately strengthens fibre-matrix adhesion. Studies indicate that alkali-treated PALF composites have a 20-40% improvement in strength and bending ability compared to untreated ones [37].

Silane coupling agents create strong links between the hydroxyl groups on the fibre surface and the functional groups in the polymer matrix [38]. Acetylation and maleated coupling, like MAPP (maleic anhydride PP), are standard methods, especially for thermoplastic materials

[39]. Physical methods such as plasma and corona discharge treatments are gaining interest because they are environmentally friendly and can activate fibre surfaces without the use of chemicals [40].

Kloykamol Panyasart et al. performed alkaline and silane treatments to modify the fibres and enhance the compatibility and composite properties of PALF/polyamide 6 composites. The raw PALF was treated with 5 wt% NaOH at ambient temperature for 5 hours (a 30:1 solution-to-fibre ratio), followed by neutralization with acetic acid. Subsequently, silane treatment was performed using APDES (3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane) in a water-ethanol solution (pH 4), after which the material was washed thoroughly and oven-dried at 70 °C for 24 hours to yield NaOH-treated PALF and Silane-treated PALF [53].

Najeeb et al. optimized silane treatments on desiccated PALF. The PALF was submerged in distilled water with a 2% Triethoxy(ethyl)silane solution, maintaining a solution-to-fibre ratio of 30:1 and a constant pH of 4. The fibres were immersed for a specific duration, rinsed with distilled water to neutralize the pH, and then oven-dried at 80 °C for 48 hours [54].

Laftah et al. investigated PALF surface treatment using polyvinyl acetate (PVA) based sizing, with glycerol as a plasticiser and urea as a stabiliser. The fibres were soaked in the solution for one hour at 70 °C. This study reveals that sizing agents enhance the handling and physical properties of PALF, reinforcing its potential as a viable alternative for textile applications [55].

The study by G.M.A. Khan et al. assessed the viability of PALF fibre as a reinforcement in the PP matrix, using alkali treatment to enhance mechanical properties. Fibre bundles were immersed in a 10% NaOH (pH 12.8) solution for 10 hours, subsequently neutralized with 1% acetic acid (CH₃COOH), rinsed with deionized water, and dried at 50°C for 24 hours [56]. Table S3 encompasses surface treatment and fibre modification parameters of PALF used in different studies.

3.4. Matrix compatibility and composite fabrication techniques

Researchers have investigated PALF in conjunction with both thermosetting and thermoplastic polymers. Epoxy resin is the predominant thermoset due to its exceptional mechanical strength and ease of production. Particularly in construction and industrial applications, unsaturated polyesters and phenolic resins are used. PALF has successfully reinforced thermoplastics, including PP, PE, and polyvinyl chloride, as well as biodegradable polymers such as PLA [45]. Various fabrication procedures are employed depending on the polymer's characteristics and intended application. Hand lay-up and compression molding are appropriate for small-scale, cost-effective production. Compression molding, specifically, ensures improved load

distribution and matrix infiltration, both of which are essential for achieving a uniform composite structure. Injection molding and extrusion are preferred methods for thermoplastics, particularly in the manufacturing of automobile components and consumer products. RTM and vacuum infusion are employed to manufacture intricate geometries and high-performance structural composites, especially with woven PALF mats [46, 47].

PALF composites can also be fabricated through hybridization, in which PALF is blended with other fibres, such as glass, jute, or carbon. This technique is explored to overcome specific performance limitations, particularly in improving impact resistance and reducing moisture absorption [48].

Badyanka et al. conducted a study on epoxy-based hybrid composites reinforced with banana, sisal, and pineapple fibers. The results demonstrated significantly enhanced mechanical and thermal properties, including higher tensile and flexural strengths, greater impact resistance, and a higher heat distortion temperature. These improvements were attributed to better fibre-matrix adhesion, as confirmed through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis [49].

Asim et al. studied PALF-reinforced PE composites and found that surface-treated fibres significantly improved interfacial adhesion, increased the storage modulus, and altered the composite's phase behaviour. At elevated temperatures, PALF degraded earlier than the polymer matrix, and Cole-Cole analysis revealed distinct phase characteristics, indicating enhanced material compatibility and performance [5].

Cherian et al. investigated the effectiveness of the high-pressure hydrothermal process on PALF. They fabricated PALF/PP composites via melt-mixing, prepregging, and compression molding. The study revealed that composites with 30 wt% PALF loading exhibited significantly better mechanical properties than those with 5 wt% PALF loading [51].

Kengkhetkit et al. devised a mechanical milling technique to obtain finer, higher-yield PALF from shredded pineapple leaves. They showed that randomly oriented PALF/PP composites produced via compression molding exhibited optimal tensile strength and hardness at 30 wt% fibre loading, attributed to enhanced fibre-matrix adhesion [52]. Table S4 outlines the matrix compatibility and fabrication techniques employed in different PALF composite studies.

3.5. Mechanical and thermal properties of PALF composites

Results from various research studies indicate that PALF significantly enhances the strength and toughness of polymer composites. PALF/epoxy composites with 30% fibre content can have tensile strengths over 120 MPa and flexural strengths that may go beyond 150 MPa, depending on how the fibres are arranged and how well they bond with the matrix. These

characteristics are advantageous compared with glass fibre-reinforced composites, particularly for weight-specific strength [67, 68].

The thermal performance of PALF composites is significantly noteworthy. TGA reveals that PALF composites begin to decompose between 260 and 280°C, with further breakdown occurring around 330-350°C due to cellulose decomposition. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analysis indicates notable alterations in the melting behaviour and crystalline structure of thermoplastic materials upon the addition of PALF. Increased stiffness and enhanced dynamic load resistance are observed in composites with PALF, as indicated by Dynamic Mechanical Analysis results. The glass transition temperature (T_g) often varies somewhat with fibre-matrix interactions and crystallinity [69].

Researchers Awad et al. found that combining alkali-treated oil palm fibre (OPF) and PALF within a bio-phenolic matrix significantly enhanced chemical interactions, mechanical properties, interfacial adhesion, thermal stability, and flexural strength. Notably, a composite with 50% PALF achieved a flexural modulus of 99.8 MPa and a tensile modulus of 7535.2 MPa. Alkali-treated hybrid bio-fibre composites are a promising approach to producing biodegradable, environmentally friendly materials for engineering and industrial applications [68].

Zin et al. investigated banana/PALF/glass hybrid composites and reported that alkaline treatment effectively enhanced the interfacial bonding between the fibres and matrix, thereby improving overall composite integrity. At 40 wt% fibre loading, peak flexural strength was recorded at 90.951 MPa for banana-glass and 105.087 MPa for PALF-glass hybrids, while flexural modulus values reached 4.219 GPa and 7.613 GPa, respectively. TGA confirmed that the composite exhibited the highest onset of thermal degradation at increased fibre loading. Additionally, dynamic mechanical analysis revealed a shift in the T_g from 30 wt% to 40 wt%, which indicates greater molecular rigidity and improved structural stability [67].

Lee et al. highlight the growing use of PALF as a reinforcement material in polymer composites, primarily because of its high cellulose content. PALF exhibits impressive mechanical properties, including a tensile strength of 126–1627 MPa, a Young's modulus of 4.2–82 GPa, elongation at break ranging from 0.8–4%, and a micro-fibrillar angle between 8° and 15°. The study also addresses prevalent modification techniques, such as silane and alkaline treatments, along with essential future considerations for their application [39]. Table S5 summarizes the mechanical and thermal properties of PALF composites reported in various studies.

4.3 Compatibility with polymer matrices

As with other plant-based fibres, the hydrophilic nature of taro fibre limits compatibility with hydrophobic polymers, thus necessitating appropriate surface treatment.

Researchers have investigated various chemical and physical surface treatments to improve fibre-matrix interaction. Among them, alkaline treatment with NaOH has been the most widely researched and used. By removing lignin, hemicellulose, and surface contaminants, alkaline treatment enhances surface roughness and reveals more cellulose microfibrils. This results in improved wettability and adhesion with polymer matrices [68]. Other methods, such as silane coupling agents, acetylation, and enzymes, have shown promise for improving interface bonding. Improved adhesion is often observed between treated taro fibres and biodegradable polymers such as PLA or polyhydroxyalkanoates, whereas untreated petroleum-based polymers typically exhibit weaker bonding [69, 70].

Experimental studies have shown that surface-modified taro fibres can substantially improve the mechanical properties of polymer composites. Using treated taro fibres in mixtures of epoxy, polyester, or PLA has resulted in a more even spread of fibres, fewer gaps, and stronger connections between the fibres and the surrounding material. These enhancements highlight the potential of taro fibres as effective reinforcement materials, especially when suitably surface-modified [71, 72].

Reddy et al. developed biodegradable bioplastic sheets by incorporating bentonite as a filler in taro fibre-reinforced films. The inclusion of bentonite increased tensile strength while decreasing swelling and water vapour transmission, which indicates enhanced mechanical and barrier properties [73].

Sun et al. investigated the enhancement of maize starch films by integrating taro fibre nanoparticles (TSNPs). Tensile strength and thermal stability of the films were improved by using TSNPs, accompanied by a reduction in water vapour permeability. The research indicated that TSNPs might significantly enhance the functional characteristics of starch-based films [74].

As an effort to produce eco-friendly packaging materials, Fansuri explored biodegradable films made from taro fibre and chitosan, with castor oil added to enhance plasticity. The films demonstrated enhanced tensile strength and thermal stability with higher chitosan content. By reducing water absorption, chitosan improved interfacial compatibility with taro fibre in the composite matrix [75]. The compatibility of taro fibres with various polymer matrices, as reported in multiple studies, is summarized in Table S7.

4.4 Reported studies on taro-based composites

Although taro fibres are relatively new in the field of composite materials, several studies have investigated their reinforcement potential in both thermoset and thermoplastic matrices. Taro powder has been effectively incorporated into recycled high-density PE/ethylene-vinyl acetate composites, which improved the modulus and thermal stability [68]. Similarly, taro starch-based bioplastic films reinforced with bentonite exhibited enhanced tensile strength, barrier properties, and biodegradability [76].

A separate study generated biodegradable composites with PLA and taro fibres for eco-friendly packaging materials. The results showed that adding 15-20% taro fibre made the composites stiffer and more heat-resistant, even though it slightly reduced their ability to stretch before breaking. The findings also demonstrated that taro fibres can substantially enhance mechanical strength while maintaining ease of processing and environmental sustainability [77].

Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of *Colocasia esculenta* (taro) starch as a renewable feedstock for the development of biodegradable bioplastics. Taro starch, derived from the tuber or peel, acts as a polymer matrix capable of forming flexible, transparent films, while additives and fillers improve its mechanical and barrier properties [78]. Shanmathy et al. produced bioplastic films from taro starch reinforced with bentonite clay, thereby improving tensile strength and reducing water vapour transmission. The films exhibited uniform morphology and complete biodegradability, which confirms that taro starch is a viable base for sustainable packaging materials [76].

Bidari et al. optimized taro peel starch-glycerol films using response surface methodology and reported higher transparency, improved flexibility, and complete degradation within 5 days in soil and river water, confirming their environmental compatibility [79].

Arini et al. concentrate on developing biofoam materials as an alternative to Styrofoam for food packaging applications. In this study, different compositions of taro fibre and PVA were assessed using a thermal compaction process to identify the most favourable mechanical and biodegradable properties [80]. Research findings on taro-based biopolymer composites and their potential applications are summarized in Table S8.

Collectively, these investigations confirm that taro starch, rather than fibre, functions as the principal biopolymer matrix in bioplastic fabrication. Reinforcing agents such as bentonite, carrageenan, and PCL enhance the strength and stability of the films without compromising biodegradability, emphasizing the versatility of taro starch for sustainable materials engineering.

4.5 Challenges in utilization and future prospects

The commercial and industrial implementation of taro fibre-reinforced composites encounters numerous obstacles. The primary challenge lies in the lack of standardized methods for fibre extraction, processing, and treatment. Consequently, differences in fibre quality and composite efficiency emerge, which makes it difficult for manufacturers to adopt taro-derived products within uniform production systems. The high hygroscopicity of untreated fibres can cause dimensional changes, microbial growth, and long-term degradation of mechanical strength.

Although alkali treatment remains the most commonly reported surface modification for taro fibre, its dominance largely reflects the limited scope of existing studies rather than an absence of alternative strategies. Recent literature on lignocellulosic fibres highlights environmentally benign approaches such as enzymatic treatments (e.g., cellulase and laccase) and plasma surface modification as promising options for improving fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion. These techniques selectively modify the fibre surface or remove non-cellulosic components while preserving the cellulose structure, and therefore are unlikely to compromise the inherent biodegradability of taro fibre. The limited application of such advanced treatments to taro fibre composites represents a clear research gap and an important direction for future investigation. A further obstacle is the limited awareness and accessibility of taro fibre in international markets. In contrast to other natural fibres such as jute, flax, and hemp, which have established supply chains and commercial viability, taro is predominantly underutilized and confined to localized, small-scale applications. The processing of taro fibres is labour-intensive, potentially constraining scalability in the absence of mechanical harvesting and fibre extraction methods. Taro fibre shows promising potential for future use in composite applications, especially as an eco-friendly, biodegradable alternative to synthetic reinforcements in applications where high strength is not essential. Possible applications encompass non-structural elements in the automotive industry, packaging materials, interior panels, insulation boards, and consumer goods.

Advancements in surface treatment techniques, hybridization with other fibres, and the extraction of nanofibers are expected to significantly enhance the performance and commercial appeal of taro fibre-based composites. Additionally, comprehensive studies on fibre-matrix interactions, thermal degradation behaviour, water absorption characteristics, and lifecycle assessment will be crucial for the successful commercialization of these composites. Figure S6 illustrates the challenges associated with the use of taro fibre-reinforced polymer-based composites, as well as their future prospects.

5.2 Mechanical, chemical, and structural properties

Banana fibres represent mechanical properties that are similar to those of other extensively researched natural fibres, including jute, hemp, and flax. The tensile strength of untreated banana fibres generally falls between 250 MPa and 500 MPa, influenced by factors such as plant variety, climatic conditions, extraction method, and pseudostem maturity. With a Young's modulus between 10 and 30 GPa, the fibre demonstrates sufficient stiffness for potential use in structural applications. The elongation at break between 1% and 3.5% suggests the fibre possesses a moderate degree of flexibility. The relatively low density of banana fibre (1.35–1.50 g/cm³) makes it a compelling choice for lightweight composite applications in aerospace and automotive sectors [81].

Chemically, banana fibres are predominantly composed of cellulose, which constitutes approximately 60-65% of their total dry weight. Cellulose provides mechanical strength and stiffness due to its crystalline structure and strong hydrogen bonding between molecular chains. Hemicellulose, at around 15-20%, imparts the fibre with notable moisture affinity and flexibility. Lignin, which constitutes about 5–10% of the fibre, is crucial for providing rigidity and thermal stability. Minor constituents such as pectin, waxes, and ash are also present, typically at 3–5%, and play a role in determining surface characteristics and adhesion behaviour with polymer matrices. The fibre's hydrophilic nature, attributed to its hydroxyl groups, limits its compatibility with hydrophobic matrices such as PP, PE, and epoxy resin [11].

The structural morphology of banana fibres is defined by their multicellular arrangement and hollow tubular form, including a central lumen extending along their length. The presence of this lumen significantly enhances the fibre's low density and thermal insulation. The surface morphology of raw banana fibre typically exhibits a rough and irregular texture, attributed to the presence of non-cellulosic components. A reduction in interfacial bonding due to this characteristic may limit stress transfer efficiency within the composite structure [82, 83]. SEM analyzes reveal microfibrils oriented at an angle to the fibre axis, resulting in anisotropic properties that influence mechanical performance under different loading directions [84].

Preethi et al. investigated the physical and chemical properties of banana fibres extracted from the pseudostem and peduncles of four commercial banana cultivars grown in Tamil Nadu, India. The study assessed fibre yield, mechanical characteristics, and chemical composition using standardized methodologies. Poovan cultivar exhibited the highest fibre recovery from the pseudostem (2.71%), while Nendran showed superior cellulose content in both peduncle (60.41%) and pseudostem fibres (59.22%). Nendran peduncle fibres also demonstrated the best

mechanical performance with the highest breaking load (3.26 N), extension (2.01 %), and tenacity (22.92 g tex⁻¹). The study demonstrates that banana biomass, particularly the pseudostem and peduncle, can be harnessed as green alternatives to synthetic fibres in industrial applications. The study's findings contribute to the valorization of agricultural waste and promote the development of eco-friendly materials [85].

The review by Bhatnagar et al. explores banana fibres as promising candidates for replacing synthetic fibres in composite materials, based on their chemical and mechanical properties. This work investigates how different treatments affect banana fibre characteristics and compares them with those of other natural fibres. It further emphasizes the environmental benefits and practical applications of banana fibre composites in industries such as automotive and construction [86].

Raon et al. conducted an in-depth investigation into the mechanical performance of banana fibre-reinforced composites, with particular emphasis on the manufacturing processes involved in their development. The study explored critical parameters influencing composite behaviour, including various fibre-treatment methods to improve strength and durability, the quality of fibre-matrix adhesion, and the influence of key processing parameters such as temperature, pressure, and curing time. By systematically analyzing these variables, the research provides valuable insights into how the mechanical properties of natural fibre composites can be enhanced. The findings support the optimization of banana fibre composites for a wide range of industrial applications, including packaging, automotive, and construction sectors [87].

Subramanya et al. examined the use of UV (ultra-violet) irradiation as a physical treatment method for *Musa sapientum* banana fibres. The results indicated mild improvements in tensile strength and surface roughness, primarily due to the elimination of non-cellulosic impurities that often hinder fibre-matrix interaction. Significantly, this method enhanced mechanical bonding without inducing significant chemical changes, making it a potentially viable and environmentally friendly approach for reinforcing natural fibre composites. [88]. The summary of research findings on banana fibre properties, treatments, and applications is outlined in Table S9.

5.3 Surface treatment and fibre-matrix adhesion

Like other natural fibres, banana fibre requires surface modification to improve adhesion with polymer matrices [89].

Alkali treatment, commonly performed with NaOH, is one of the most effective and widely used methods for modifying banana fibre [90]. This treatment removes amorphous components

such as hemicellulose, lignin, pectin, and surface waxes, thereby increasing surface roughness and exposing the reactive hydroxyl groups of cellulose. As a result, the fibre exhibits improved wettability and mechanical interlocking with the matrix. Moreover, alkali-treated fibres exhibit increased crystallinity, resulting in higher stiffness and tensile strength of the final composite [91].

A prevalent technique for surface modification of banana fibre is silane treatment, which employs silane coupling agents to establish covalent bonds between the fibre and the polymer matrix. These agents interact with hydroxyl groups on the fibre surface to form siloxane linkages while simultaneously engaging functional groups in the polymer matrix, thereby serving as a molecular bridge. Acetylation is applied to banana fibres to reduce their hydrophilicity by replacing hydroxyl groups with acetyl groups, thereby reducing water absorption and swelling. Maleic anhydride grafted compatibilizers, such as maleic anhydride grafted PP (MAPP), are frequently employed in thermoplastic matrices to enhance compatibility and stress transfer [92, 93].

The efficacy of surface treatments is typically validated using characterization techniques like Scanning Electron Microscope, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, and contact angle measurements. Surface-treated banana fibre composites show significant improvements in tensile strength (typically 20-30%) and overall durability compared to untreated composites, highlighting the vital role of surface engineering in advancing natural fibre composite development [94].

The study by Gupta and Tiwari et al. demonstrated that optimizing low-pressure oxygen plasma treatment can substantially improve the surface characteristics and adhesion properties of banana and sisal fibres. By improving the mechanical properties of epoxy-based composites, these modifications support their adoption in sustainable industries where durability and performance are critical [95].

Alonso et al. evaluated the effects of organosilane treatment on raw banana fibres and observed notable improvements in surface morphology, increased porosity, and enhanced basicity. Through inverse gas chromatography analysis, it was confirmed that the surface modifications facilitated covalent bonding between silane compounds and cellulose chains, thereby enhancing fibre-matrix adhesion. Among the organosilane agents, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) are commonly used for fibre modification. TEOS acts as a silica precursor, increasing surface roughness and providing silanol groups for bonding, whereas APTES introduces amino functional groups capable of forming covalent bonds with the polymer matrix. These mechanisms collectively strengthen

interfacial adhesion and improve the overall mechanical integrity of banana fibre composites [96].

The review by Gupta et al. demonstrated that among multiple surface modification techniques, alkali and silane treatments were notably effective. By markedly improving fibre-matrix adhesion and mechanical performance in banana fibre composites, they support their application as sustainable and viable options in industry [97].

According to Uthayakumar et al., the chemical surface treatment of banana fibres with silanes and 1% NaOH significantly enhanced fibre-matrix adhesion in polyester composites, accompanied by improved tensile and flexural characteristics, as confirmed by scanning electron microscope, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, and electrokinetic methods [98]. Table S10 details the impact of surface treatments on fibre tensile strength, surface energy, and interfacial shear strength (IFSS), along with essential observations from multiple studies.

5.4 Performance of banana fibre composites

Banana fibre-reinforced polymer composites exhibit significant improvements in mechanical performance when optimized factors, such as fibre volume fraction, fibre length, orientation, and matrix selection, are considered. Well-fabricated banana fibre composites exhibit tensile strengths ranging from 40 to 60 MPa, which are influenced by the matrix type and the extent of fibre treatment. The material can withstand bending forces, with flexural strengths ranging from 50 to 70 MPa. The enhancement of impact strength is notably pronounced, especially in hybrid composites that integrate banana fibres with various natural or synthetic fibres to achieve an optimal balance of strength and toughness [99].

TGA and DSC were used to evaluate the thermal properties of banana fibre composites. TGA results typically show the onset of thermal degradation at 250–300°C, making these composites suitable for use with thermoplastics such as PE, PP, and PLA, as well as some epoxy-based thermosets. DSC studies indicate that treated fibres promote nucleation during polymer crystallization, resulting in increased crystallinity and enhanced thermal stability [100].

Moisture absorption remains a significant constraint on the performance of banana fibre composites. The inherent hydrophilicity of the fibres results in water absorption, which can cause swelling, plasticization, and a gradual decline in mechanical properties over time. This presents significant challenges in outdoor or humid environments. The selection of surface treatment and matrix can effectively reduce this effect, as hydrophobic matrices and fibre coatings serve as efficient barriers to moisture penetration [97, 101].

Banana fibre composites are utilized across multiple sectors due to their lightweight nature, biodegradability, and sufficient rigidity. In the automotive industry, these materials find application in interior panels, trims, and non-structural components. The construction industry uses these composites to produce partition boards, ceiling panels, and insulation materials. In the consumer goods field, these items are being integrated into furniture, packaging materials, and biodegradable utensils. Moreover, banana fibre composites are increasingly being embraced in the sustainable fashion and textile sectors, especially for the creation of eco-friendly footwear and accessories [102].

The extensive review by Sivaranjana et al. examined numerous hybrid composites that integrate banana fibres with other natural or synthetic fibres. It emphasizes improvements in mechanical and thermal properties resulting from hybridization and fibre treatments [103].

By optimizing the filler content, Ganasan et al. found that adding banana fibre and eggshell powder to epoxy matrices increased mechanical strength and thermal stability and decreased moisture absorption [104].

Zaman et al. found that banana fibre-reinforced PP composites exhibit improved thermal degradation resistance and better matrix–fibre compatibility when manufactured via melt compounding and analyzed through TGA [105].

Rajamanickam et al. demonstrated that chemical surface treatment of banana fibre significantly enhances their interfacial bonding within phenolic resin matrices. This improved fibre-matrix adhesion contributes to better load transfer efficiency, resulting in notable enhancements in both mechanical strength and morphological characteristics of the composites [106]. The performance characteristics of treated banana fibre composites with different polymer matrices and surface treatments, as reported in multiple studies, are presented in Table S11.

6.1 Fibre properties and chemical composition

The intrinsic properties of natural fibres substantially affect the effectiveness of polymer composites. Pineapple, taro, and banana fibres demonstrate significant variations in density, tensile strength, elongation, and chemical composition, especially in cellulose concentration.

Pineapple fibre has a notable cellulose content of 81%, which enhances its stiffness and mechanical strength. The fibre possesses a density of 1.52 g/cm³ and a tensile strength of 413 MPa, with a low elongation at break of approximately 1.6%. These numbers indicate its rigidity and limited ductility. The elevated cellulose content, coupled with minimal elongation, yields significant reinforcement potential when stiffness and dimensional stability are essential. Banana fibre has the highest tensile strength of the three, at 529 MPa. Its density is marginally

less than that of pineapple fibre (1.35 g/cm^3), and with an elongation at break of 3.5%, it demonstrates improved flexibility and energy dissipation. The cellulose percentage of banana fibre is 65.28%, which, while lower than that of pineapple, nonetheless enhances mechanical performance when paired with its superior elongation capacity. The mechanical performance of taro fibre is relatively low, as indicated by its tensile strength of 190-300 MPa and a density of 1.32 g/cm^3 . It exhibits a comparatively higher elongation at break of 3.47%, indicative of superior flexibility relative to pineapple fibre. The cellulose content of taro fibre is the lowest among these three fibres, recorded at 63.85%. The low cellulose concentration and high hemicellulose content account for its restricted reinforcing effectiveness and increased vulnerability to breakdown [81, 107, 108]. Table S12 presents a summary comparison of the properties and chemical composition of PALF, taro, and banana fibres to facilitate a better understanding of their structural and functional differences.

6.2 Matrix compatibility and interfacial bonding

Natural fibres inherently exhibit hydrophilic characteristics due to the presence of hydroxyl groups in their cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin components. Among the studied fibres in this review, banana fibre demonstrated the most significant improvement in interfacial adhesion following alkali treatment. The SEM images presented in the scientific paper reveal that banana fibres form a well-integrated surface within the polymer matrix, with minimal voids or fibre pull-out. This points to effective mechanical interlocking, attributed to increased surface roughness and fibrillation that enhance the grip of the fibre within the matrix. Although PALF contains a higher cellulose fraction, cellulose content alone does not dictate fibre-matrix adhesion because adhesion is governed primarily by surface activation, wettability, and the extent of fibrillation after treatment. The consistently superior fibre-matrix interface observed in banana fibre composites, despite the lower intrinsic cellulose content compared to PALF, can be attributed to differences in surface morphology and fibrillation behavior. Alkali treatment induces more pronounced fibrillation and surface roughening in banana fibres, thereby increasing the effective surface area and promoting mechanical interlocking with the matrix. SEM observations reveal improved wetting, minimal interfacial voids, and reduced fibre pull-out in banana fibre composites, indicating more uniform stress transfer. In contrast, PALF, although richer in cellulose, exhibits comparatively limited fibrillation and occasional interfacial gaps, likely due to its higher stiffness and lower elongation capacity. These structural and morphological factors collectively govern interfacial efficiency more strongly than cellulose content alone. Alkali treatment appears to induce stronger fibrillation and higher

surface roughness in banana fibre, thereby improving mechanical interlocking and producing a more continuous interface with minimal voids or pull-out. In contrast, alkali-treated PALF often shows only slight fibrillation and may retain minor interfacial gaps, which reduces bonding uniformity despite its higher cellulose level. PALF treated with alkali solutions exhibits enhanced compatibility with the matrix, attributed to surface cleaning and removal of amorphous components. Scanning electron microscopy analysis supports these improvements, showing better adhesion and fewer gaps at the interface. However, the bonding uniformity is slightly lower than that achieved with alkali-treated banana fibre. In contrast, taro fibre exhibits a comparatively limited response to alkali treatment. SEM analysis reported in the existing research reveals marked fibre pull-out, insufficient wetting, and interfacial voids, indicative of reduced fibre-matrix adhesion. This subpar interfacial bonding is primarily attributed to the elevated hemicellulose content and less favourable surface morphology of taro fibres, which hinder effective interaction with the polymer matrix. As a result, taro fibre-reinforced composites tend to demonstrate inferior mechanical improvements when compared to those reinforced with banana or pineapple fibres [34, 109, 110]. The scenario of compatibility and interfacial bonding among PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites is shown in Table S13.

6.3 Processing methods and ease of fabrication

Natural fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites, including those incorporating banana, pineapple, and taro fibres, can be fabricated using melt-compounding techniques, such as Brabender mixing, followed by hot-press molding at approximately 180 °C. Despite the standard processing route, fibre-specific characteristics significantly influence mixing behaviour, dispersion quality, and composite homogeneity. Banana fibres exhibit superior compatibility with the thermoplastic matrix during processing. Their moderate density and inherent flexibility facilitate uniform dispersion without significant fibre degradation. These attributes contribute to the preservation of structural integrity during both compounding and molding stages, resulting in composites with consistent mechanical properties. Pineapple fibres also perform well under melt processing, although their relatively higher stiffness can occasionally hinder uniform dispersion. Nonetheless, appropriate control of processing parameters, such as mixing speed and temperature, helps to minimize fibre damage and promotes adequate fibre-matrix interaction. This results in homogeneous composite sheets with reliable mechanical performance. In contrast, taro fibres present greater challenges during melt processing. Their lower mechanical strength and sensitivity to thermal stress increase the likelihood of fibre fracture. Moreover, taro fibres are prone to agglomeration, which leads to

uneven dispersion and the formation of micro-voids within the matrix. These issues reduce the structural uniformity of the composite and may compromise its mechanical stability [18, 111]. Table S14 represents the processing methods and ease of fabrication of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites.

6.4 Mechanical and thermal performance

The mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced composites differ significantly depending on the type of natural fibre, due to variations in fibre strength, interfacial bonding, and dispersion quality. According to published studies, banana fibre composites exhibit the highest mechanical performance, with tensile strength reaching a high level and flexural strength in an elevated range. These values reflect strong interfacial adhesion, high intrinsic fibre strength, and a uniform fibre distribution during processing. The composites also exhibit elevated elongation at break, indicating a favourable balance between strength and ductility. PALF composites demonstrate moderately high mechanical performance. Reported tensile and flexural strengths indicate efficient reinforcement capacity, supported by high cellulose content and acceptable interfacial compatibility. Despite this, slightly reduced elongation at break and occasional voids between the fibre and matrix limit the mechanical reliability when compared to banana fibre composites. Taro fibre composites show the lowest mechanical strength among the three types. Tensile and flexural strengths are comparatively lower. Although the elongation at break appears somewhat improved, the reduced strength indicates weak interfacial bonding, poor fibre distribution, and low inherent fibre strength. These limitations restrict the use of taro fibre composites to non-structural or low-load applications. Thermal analysis supports these observations. Banana fibre composites exhibit the highest onset degradation temperatures, which confirms superior thermal stability. Pineapple fibre composites also maintain considerable thermal resistance. In contrast, taro fibre composites begin to degrade at lower temperatures. This behaviour results from a lower cellulose content and a higher proportion of hemicellulose and lignin, which decompose at relatively reduced temperatures. These thermal limitations further constrain their applicability in environments exposed to sustained heat [17, 34, 112, 113]. Table S15 outlines the mechanical and thermal performance of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites.

Beyond single-fibre systems, synergy can arise when two or all three agro-waste fibres are combined within the same composite. A PALF-banana hybrid is expected to deliver a stiffness-toughness balance because PALF contributes rigidity via its high cellulose content and low elongation, while banana provides higher ductility and typically stronger fibre–matrix bonding

after alkali treatment, which supports improved stress transfer and reduced fibre pull-out. This complementary reinforcement can elevate tensile/flexural performance relative to PALF alone and can reduce brittle failure tendencies. Incorporating taro fibre can further tailor ductility, damping, biodegradability, and potentially thermal insulation. Yet, taro-rich formulations may reduce strength unless taro remains a minor fraction and undergoes more substantial surface modification or compatibilization, as taro commonly exhibits weak interfacial bonding and a risk of agglomeration. Therefore, the most practical all-natural design space is a PALF-banana structural backbone with controlled taro addition to confer functional attributes, rather than relying exclusively on synthetic-fibre hybridization.

6.5 Moisture absorption and thermal stability

Moisture absorption and thermal stability are critical parameters for assessing the durability and processing suitability of natural fibre-reinforced polymer composites. Surface treatment modifies fibre chemistry and interfacial interactions, which directly influence these properties [10,12–15].

Treated lignocellulosic fibres exhibit reduced moisture uptake due to the partial removal of hemicellulose, lignin, surface waxes, and other amorphous constituents, which decreases the availability of hydrophilic hydroxyl groups and improves fibre-matrix adhesion [68, 89-91]. Alkali-treated PALF composites show reduced water absorption compared with untreated systems, particularly at higher treatment concentrations and optimized fibre loadings, which has been attributed to enhanced fibre-matrix compatibility and reduced interfacial voids [48, 51, 59]. Treated banana pseudo-stem fibre composites similarly exhibit lower moisture absorption after alkali or silane treatment, resulting from improved surface roughness, increased crystallinity, and stronger interfacial bonding with the polymer matrix [90-94]. In contrast, quantitative moisture absorption data for treated taro fibre-reinforced polymer composites remain limited. Existing studies on taro-based systems primarily report moisture content, water solubility, or water vapour transmission behaviour of taro-derived films and matrices rather than standardized composite water absorption measurements, underscoring the need for further systematic investigation of treated taro fibre composite systems [73, 74, 79]. TGA demonstrates that surface treatment enhances the thermal stability of natural fibres and their composites by reducing thermally unstable components and improving structural uniformity [56, 112]. Treated PALF composites typically exhibit thermal degradation onset at 260-280°C, with a subsequent primary decomposition associated with cellulose degradation at higher temperatures, depending on fibre content and matrix type [54-56, 112]. Alkali-treated

banana fibre composites exhibit comparable thermal behaviour, with improved onset degradation temperatures and enhanced resistance to thermal decomposition due to increased crystallinity and stronger fibre-matrix interactions [49, 56, 99]. Taro fibre-based systems exhibit comparatively lower thermal stability, and thermal decomposition typically initiates in the range of 200-250°C. Studies on taro-derived matrices and taro fibre-reinforced films report an initial mass-loss stage below 300 °C, followed by a primary thermal degradation stage at higher temperatures. Composite-level onset degradation temperatures for treated taro fibre systems remain less consistently documented across different polymer matrices, which limits direct cross-system comparison [70, 79].

6.6 Environmental impact and biodegradability

Natural fibre-reinforced composites offer sustainable advantages, particularly in terms of renewability, biodegradability, and end-of-life disposal. Fibres such as PALF, banana, and taro are derived from agricultural byproducts, thereby adding value to biomass that would otherwise go to waste [114]. Soil burial experiments are commonly performed over specific durations to evaluate the biodegradability of natural fibre-based composites under soil conditions [115]. The deterioration of taro fibre composites indicates their significant susceptibility to environmental degradation [116]. This characteristic renders taro composites especially appropriate for packaging and throwaway applications, where a brief lifecycle and rapid breakdown are preferred [7]. Banana and pineapple fibre composites undergo biodegradation, though to a lesser extent. Banana fibre composites show a measurable decrease in mass, while pineapple fibre composites demonstrate a relatively higher loss [81]. These degradation characteristics enable a compromise between useful service life and eventual natural decay, making the materials suitable for semi-structural applications that require reliable durability before eco-conscious disposal [117]. From an environmental standpoint, these three fibres facilitate waste valorization, diminish reliance on plastics, and alleviate the ecological risks associated with synthetic fibres. Taro fibre composites, despite their limited mechanical strength, exhibit rapid degradation, whereas banana and pineapple fibre composites deliver enhanced structural integrity with a moderate environmental decomposition [118]. Table S16 shows the ecological impact and biodegradability of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites.

6.7 Performance trend of hybrid composites (bridging single-fibre and high-performance requirements)

In addition to single-fibre systems, multiple investigations show that hybrid composites that combine agro-waste fibres with another natural fibre or a limited fraction of a synthetic fibre

(e.g., glass) can provide a step-change in stiffness, flexural performance, and damage tolerance relative to single-fibre composites, because the secondary reinforcement improves load sharing and constrains crack growth. In this context, hybridization is frequently reported as a pragmatic route to overcome key limitations of purely natural-fibre composites, particularly impact resistance and moisture-related durability, while still maintaining partial sustainability when the natural fibre fraction remains dominant.

A representative example is the Banana/PALF/Glass hybrid system, where reported flexural strength and modulus reach ~105.1 MPa and ~7.61 GPa, respectively (at 40 wt% reinforcement), together with a Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) observed T_g shift that indicates increased molecular rigidity and improved structural stability [56]. These results align with the broader observation that hybridization of PALF with other fibres (including glass) is explicitly pursued to address performance gaps such as moisture sensitivity and impact limitations. Therefore, the performance ranking discussed for the three single-fibre composite families (PALF, banana, taro) should be interpreted as the baseline. At the same time, hybrid designs represent an additional design lever that can outperform the baseline when higher structural performance is required.

6.8 Qualitative economic perspective on material cost

Because this work is a review, the manuscript does not provide a single, standardized formulation (fibre wt%, exact treatment recipe, compatibilizer loading, processing yield, or regional feedstock costs). Therefore, an absolute cost-per-kilogram estimate is not defensible based on the present dataset. Even so, current literature supports a directional comparison. Glass fibre used for composites is commonly reported at roughly USD 1.3-2.0 per kg (fibre only), which provides a practical baseline for Glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (GFRPP) composites-cost discussions [119].

For PALF, banana fibre, and taro fibre composites, the primary economic advantage originates from the use of agricultural residues as fibre sources. The manuscript highlights that pineapple leaves and banana pseudostems are agro-waste materials, and their utilization can reduce raw material costs while supporting waste valorization. However, the supplementary discussion also emphasizes that chemical treatments and fibre conditioning steps contribute additional costs, which must be considered when assessing the final composite material cost. Based on current literature, natural fibre-reinforced polypropylene composites are frequently reported to be cost-competitive and, in many cases, lower in material cost than GFRPP when moderate fibre loadings and conventional surface treatments are employed. Within the three agro-waste

fibres discussed in this review, banana fibre-reinforced polypropylene composites are generally expected to show the most favorable cost balance because banana pseudostems are widely available as agricultural residues and have been extensively studied for thermoplastic compounding, which supports more predictable processing behavior and lower risk of material loss. PALF composites are similarly expected to remain economically competitive due to the abundance of pineapple leaves as a byproduct and their demonstrated suitability for polymer reinforcement [120].

In contrast, the economic positioning of taro fibre-reinforced polypropylene composites remains more uncertain. Although taro petioles represent a low-cost biomass source, the manuscript notes limited industrial development and less established supply chains for taro fibre, which can increase processing complexity and variability in delivered fibre quality, thereby reducing the apparent cost advantage when compared with more mature natural fibre systems and with GFRPP.

Overall, the available literature supports the conclusion that PALF-PP and banana fibre-PP composites are likely to be lower in material cost than GFRPP on a qualitative basis. In contrast, taro fibre-PP composites may approach cost parity or exhibit a smaller cost advantage, depending on the processing route and scale. These conclusions are intentionally directional and qualitative, and a quantitative cost comparison would require standardized formulations and detailed bill-of-material data, which are beyond the scope of the present review.

7.1 Issues related to moisture absorption, fibre dispersion, and durability

Pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites face their greatest challenge because they naturally absorb moisture from their environment. All natural fibre sources, such as pineapple, taro, and banana, exhibit hygroscopic behaviour, as they draw in atmospheric humidity. The absorption process damages the fibre-polymer matrix bond and creates deterioration in the final composite material. The reduction in tensile, flexural, and impact strength is significant due to this phenomenon. Moisture absorption makes composite materials dimensionally unstable, as fibres can swell or warp, affecting the material's structural integrity.

When moisture interacts with materials, it makes them more vulnerable to microbial and fungal attacks, reducing the lifespan of composites, especially in moist or soaked conditions. The thermal stability of pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites degrades when these materials contain high moisture levels, as such conditions limit their usability in elevated-temperature applications. The longevity of pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites faces significant

challenges due to these interaction factors, particularly in outdoor and automotive or construction applications.

The distribution of fibres throughout the polymer matrix constitutes a crucial problem. Pineapple, banana, and taro fibres tend to exhibit unequal dimensions and irregular shapes, with high surface roughness, which complicates their even distribution within polymers. Mechanical property fluctuations arise due to selective support caused by the random distribution of these fibres within the composite. Composite performance deterioration is attributed to poor interfacial bonding resulting from the hydrophilic nature of pineapple, banana, and taro fibres and the hydrophobicity of the polymer matrix.

A significant challenge for pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites is their limited durability under varying environmental conditions. While biodegradation occurs in pineapple, banana, and taro fibres, it exhibits both beneficial and detrimental characteristics. While biodegradability supports ecological sustainability, it also reduces the lifespan of composite materials when exposed to harsh environmental conditions such as UV radiation, moisture, and mechanical stress.

7.2 Fibre treatment methods to enhance performance

Multiple treatments for pineapple, banana and taro fibre exist because they address issues with water absorption, dispersion, and durability. The objective of these treatments is to modify the fibre surface to better suit the matrix while boosting mechanical performance.

The alkaline treatment procedure involving NaOH application serves as one of the most common chemical techniques for removing hemicellulose and lignin from natural fibres while enhancing their surface texture and matrix-binding capabilities. The treatment results in a superior interfacial bond between the fibres and the matrix, along with improved mechanical properties. Silane coupling is a widely used method for improving interfacial bonding by forming covalent bonds between fibres and matrices. Improved fibre dispersion and composite uniformity are achieved through the breakdown of fibre structures by sulfuric acid and other acid treatments.

Physical techniques such as plasma and microwave treatment can activate surface fibres, improving dispersion and bonding performance. Plasma treatment modifies fibre surfaces by introducing reactive functional groups, thereby increasing their compatibility with polymers. Better fibre separation occurs with steam explosion treatment, enabling more effective dispersion and a lower likelihood of clumping.

The use of natural enzymes, such as cellulase and laccase, in enzymatic treatments provides environmentally friendly chemical alternatives. The enzymes enzymatically degrade non-cellulosic components of fibres, yet enhance their matrix-affinity performance without requiring any ecologically damaging chemicals.

Surface coatings of silica and titanium dioxide nanoparticles shield pineapple, banana, and taro fibres from moisture, UV degradation, and microbial attack, thereby improving fibre-matrix bonding and enhancing composite durability and mechanical properties.

7.3 Hybrid composites and nanocomposites

The invention of hybrid composites provides a strategy to overcome the mechanical limitations of purely natural fibre composites such as pineapple, banana, and taro. These composites combine natural fibres with limited proportions of synthetic fibres (e.g., glass or carbon) to achieve higher mechanical, thermal, and moisture-resistance performance. Although the inclusion of synthetic fibres appears contrary to eco-design principles, hybrid composites can still be regarded as partially sustainable when the natural component is dominant and recyclable or bio-based polymer matrices are used. This approach reduces the overall amount of synthetic material, extends product lifespan, and lowers energy consumption during use by reducing weight. In addition, current research focuses on greener alternatives such as basalt fibres and recyclable carbon fibres, which further improve environmental compatibility. Therefore, hybrid composites can serve as a transitional design toward fully sustainable materials when developed with careful consideration of recyclability and reduced environmental impact.

Besides hybrid composites, the performance of pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites can also be enhanced by fabricating nanocomposites. Nanomaterials, such as nanocellulose, carbon nanotubes, and graphene, can be incorporated into the polymer matrix to improve its properties. Nanocellulose has initially been proven to significantly strengthen the mechanical interfacial bonding between natural fibres such as pineapple, banana, and taro and the polymer matrix, due to its solvent affinity and enhanced moisture resistance. By boosting thermal stability, barrier properties, and UV resistance, nanocomposites enable pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites to be used in a range of high-performance applications. The integration of nanocellulose and other nanomaterials enhances both the performance and sustainability of composite materials. Consequently, nanocomposites represent a promising approach for developing high-performance, eco-friendly materials.

Within the context of the fibres reviewed in this work, hybrid systems such as Banana/PALF/Glass demonstrate that hybrid architectures can exceed the performance of

corresponding single-fibre composites, particularly with respect to flexural strength and stiffness. The incorporation of secondary reinforcement improves load transfer efficiency and restricts crack propagation, thereby enhancing structural stability and durability. Such performance enhancement supports the selection of hybrid composites for semi-structural and load-bearing applications where mechanical reliability and service life are critical, while still retaining a significant contribution from renewable agro-waste fibres.

7.4 Industrial scalability and commercialization potential

Even though the potential of pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites is well known in research, there is still a significant gap in achieving industrial-scale production and commercialization. The biggest problem is the standardization of the quality of fibre. Pineapple, banana, and taro fibres exhibit considerable natural variability due to factors such as plant species, growth conditions, and harvesting methods. Covariance may result in different properties in the aerospace material, and a more difficult range of large-sized units. To ensure consistent performance across large batches, it is essential to standardize the fibre extraction process and implement strict quality control measures.

To address the variability concerns associated with PALF and banana fibre and to facilitate their qualification for automotive or structural applications, existing international standardization frameworks can be systematically adopted, even though fibre-specific extraction standards are not yet available. In practice, fibre conditioning and testing in controlled environments, following ISO 139 or ASTM D1776, provide consistency in moisture-sensitive measurements [121, 122]. At the same time, single-fibre tensile characterization according to ASTM D3822 enables statistical assessment of strength dispersion and batch reliability [64]. For composite-level validation, widely accepted standards such as ASTM D3039 or ISO 527-5 for tensile properties [65, 66], ISO 14125 for flexural performance [28], and ASTM D570 or ISO 62 for moisture absorption [41, 42] offer a robust route for benchmarking PALF and banana-fibre-reinforced composites against industrial requirements. Thermal stability and compositional consistency can further be screened using thermogravimetric protocols such as ISO 11358 or ASTM E1131 [29, 30]. Although these standards were initially developed for conventional fibres and polymer composites, their adoption, combined with clearly defined extraction procedures, fibre moisture limits, and statistical reporting of property variability, provides a practical and immediately applicable quality-control roadmap for reducing batch-to-batch inconsistency and supporting the scalable

use of PALF and banana fibre in semi-structural and structural composite applications [31, 65, 123].

Another significant challenge lies in the overall product cost. While pineapple, banana, and taro fibres are naturally low-cost, processing steps, such as chemical treatments and fibre separation, substantially increase total costs. Moreover, advancing natural fibre composites for large-scale industrial applications, particularly in sectors traditionally reliant on synthetic materials like automotive and construction, will demand considerable investment in specialized infrastructure and processing equipment.

A robust supply chain for pineapple, banana, and taro fibres is essential for large-scale production. This involves securing high-quality, authentic fibres, improving harvesting and extraction methods, and maintaining sustainability throughout the supply process. Additionally, consumer adoption of pineapple, banana, and taro fibre composites depends on clear evidence of their performance compared to synthetic alternatives, along with proof of their viability and environmental benefits.

Figure S1. Extraction process of PALF and associated environmental impacts

Figure S2. Chemical and physical properties of PALF [41, 46, 47]

Figure S3. Applications of PALF composites in industry

Figure S4. A visual representation of the taro fibre extraction process

Raw taro fibers exhibit moderate tensile strength, generally between 0.19 GPa and 0.50 GPa, with a Young's modulus ranging from 6 to 9 GPa.

Figure S5. Microstructural and compositional attributes of taro fibre [87]

Figure S6. Challenges in utilization and future prospects of taro fibre reinforced polymer-based composites

Figure S7. Schematic representation of the banana pseudostem showing fibre extraction zones

Figure S8. Common challenges and opportunities in natural fibre reinforced composites, with emphasis on pineapple, taro, and banana fibres

Table S1. Chemical compositions of different natural fibres at a glance [21, 22]

Fiber Name	Cellulose (%)	Lignin (%)	Hemi Cellulose (%)	Pectin (%)	Wax (%)	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Micro fibrillar Angle (⁰)
Cotton	82.7–90	–	3	–	0.6	7.85–8.5	–	–
Pineapple	70-82	5-12.7	-	1.1	3-3.3	11.8	0.71-0.87	14
Kenaf	45–57	21.5	8–13	0.6	0.8	6.2–12	2–5	2–6.2
Jute	61–71.5	11.8-13	17.9-22.4	0.2	0.5	12.5-13.7	0.5–2	8
Hemp	70.2–74.4	3.7–5.7	17.9-22.4	0.9	0.8	6.2–12	0.8	2–6.2
Sisal	78	8	10	–	2	11	1	20–25
Flax	64.1–71.9	2.0–2.2	64.1-71.9	1.8–2.3	1.7	8–12	–	5–10

Table S2. Common techniques for composite fabrication

Processing Technique	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applications	Study
Hand Lay-Up	A manual method where fibre layers are placed in a mold and resin is applied.	Simple, low-cost, suitable for small production runs, enables manual control of fibre orientation, and requires no specialized equipment.	Labour-intensive, inconsistent quality, longer cycle time, dependent on operator skill.	Low-volume production, prototype manufacturing, automotive interiors, and consumer goods.	[51]
Compression Molding	Fibre mats or chopped fibres are placed into a heated mold and pressed to cure the resin.	High throughput, good for high-volume production, consistent material properties, and fast curing.	Limited to simple shapes, it requires precise control of fibre distribution and mold pressure.	Automotive parts, panels, and construction materials.	[52]
Injection Molding	Chopped fibres are combined with resin and injected into a heated mold under pressure.	High-speed production, good dispersion of chopped fibres, and capability for complex shapes.	Expensive molds, high energy consumption, fibre length reduction and limited control over fibre orientation.	Mass production of parts like dashboards, housings, and consumer goods.	[53]

RTM	Dry fibre preforms are placed in a mold, and liquid resin is injected under pressure to impregnate the fibre.	Excellent for complex shapes, high-quality finish, good fibre-matrix bonding, high-strength composites.	Expensive tooling, longer cycle time, may require additional equipment for resin injection.	High-performance automotive parts, aerospace, and structural applications.	[54]
Pultrusion	Continuous process where fibres are pulled through a resin bath and then through a heated die to cure.	Continuous production, high-volume capability, consistent cross-sectional shapes, high fibre content.	Limited to specific shapes (mainly profiles), slow setup time, limited flexibility in part design.	Structural components, profiles, rods, and composite pipes.	[68]

Table S3. Surface treatment and fibre modification parameters of PALF used in different studies

Solution	Neutralization	Temperature	Time	Reference
5% NaOH	Acetic acid (pH 4)	70°C	24 h	[41]
2% Triethoxy(ethyl)	-	80°C	48 h	[42]
PVA	-	70°C	1 h	[43]
10% NaOH	1% CH ₃ COOH	50°C	24 h	[44]

Table S4. Matrix compatibility and composite fabrication techniques of PALF in different studies

Material	Fabrication Method	Observations	Reference
PALF/Low-Density Polyethylene	Hand lay-up technique	Crosshead speed of 500 mm/min yields peak TS/TM and the lowest elongation observed	[49]
PALF/PP	Injection molding	50/50 fibre matrix loading exhibited highest TM, FS and FM	[5]
PALF/PP, PALF Loading -5 and 30 wt%	Melt mixing, prepreg, compression molding	PALF with 30 wt% > 5 wt% fiber loading	[51]
Randomly oriented PALF/PP	Compression molding	PALF with 30 wt% offered highest TS and hardness due to good adhesion between fiber matrix	[52]

Table S5. Mechanical and thermal properties of PALF composites in different studies

Materials	Mechanical Properties	Thermal Properties	Reference
Bio-phenolic matrix with OPF and PALF	Tensile strength: 33.3 MPa; Tensile modulus: 7.54 GPa; Flexural strength: 99.8 MPa; Flexural modulus: 8.81 GPa	Improved thermal stability	[68]
Banana/PALF/Glass fibre hybrid composites	Flexural strength (40 wt%): 105.1 MPa; Flexural modulus: 7.61 GPa	Tg shift observed by DMA (30-40 wt%)	[67]
PALF in various polymer composites	Tensile strength: 126-1627 MPa; Young's modulus: 4.2-82 GPa; Elongation: 0.8-4 %	-	[39]

Table S6. Microstructural Observations and Fibre-Matrix Interface of PALF composites in different studies

Surface Features	Fiber-Matrix Interface	Findings	Reference
PALF showed a naturally rougher surface, better epoxy impregnation	Stronger adhesion with reduced porosity	PALF composites had better interfacial bonding and superior mechanical performance compared to coir	[37]
Increased surface roughness after treatment	Enhanced adhesion and fewer voids	Surface treatment improved mechanical and thermal properties	[38]
Rough, layered epidermis with hydrophobic waxy surface; thinner fibres smoother	Better fibre-matrix interlocking in thinner fibres	Thinner PALF fibres resulted in higher composite quality with fewer defects	[39]

Table S7. Compatibility of taro fibres with various polymer matrices reported in previous studies

Polymer Matrix	Compatibility with Matrix	Findings	Reference
Bio-phenolic polymer	Improved compatibility; better dispersion of filler; enhanced mechanical strength	Bentonite reinforcement increased tensile strength, reduced swelling index, and enhanced biodegradability of taro-based films.	[58]
Corn starch	Good compatibility due to natural interaction; improved mechanical and barrier properties	Addition of TSNPs enhanced tensile strength and thermal stability, reduced water vapor permeability of corn starch films.	[30]

Chitosan	Strong interfacial bonding through hydrogen bonding and plasticization	Chitosan incorporation improved tensile strength, decreased water uptake, and enhanced thermal stability, indicating strong compatibility with taro fibre.	[59]
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Table S8. Summary of research findings on taro-derived biopolymer composites and their potential uses

Polymer Matrix	Findings	Applications	Reference
Taro Fibre with Bentonite	Enhanced tensile strength and reduced water vapor transmission rates; biodegradable	Sustainable packaging alternatives	[76]
Taro Peel Starch	Good film-forming ability; favorable mechanical and biodegradable properties	Biodegradable film production	[77]
Taro Fibre-Carrageenan with PCL	Improved tensile strength and elasticity; optimized swelling behavior and biodegradability	Bioplastic formulations for packaging	[78]
Taro Fibre with PVAc	Achieved tensile strength of 0.357 MPa and elongation of 246.4%; 91.2% biodegradability over 50 days	Biodegradable foam packaging materials	[79]

Table S9. Summary of research findings on banana fibre properties, treatments, and applications

Source	Treatment/Focus	Findings	Applications	Study
Grand Naine, Poovan, Monthan, Nendran (Tamil Nadu, India)	Assessment of fibre yield, mechanical and chemical properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poovan: Highest pseudostem fibre yield (2.71%) • Nendran: Highest cellulose content & best mechanical properties 	Green alternative to synthetic fibres; eco-materials	[85]
Banana fibres (general)	Effect of different treatments; comparison with other natural fibres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment significantly influences fibre properties • Highlights eco-friendly and industrial potential 	Automotive, construction; sustainable composites	[86]
Banana fibre-reinforced composites	Manufacturing process, fibre treatment, and processing parameter optimization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved mechanical properties through optimized treatment and processing • Better fibre-matrix adhesion 	Packaging, automotive, construction	[87]
<i>Musa sapientum</i> banana fibres	UV irradiation as physical treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mild improvement in tensile strength • Enhanced bonding without major chemical changes 	Reinforcement in natural fibre composites; eco-friendly	[88]

Table S10. Effects of different surface treatments on fibre tensile strength, surface energy, interfacial shear strength (IFSS), and observations from various studies

Treatment Type	Improvement in Tensile Strength (%)	Contact Angle / Surface Energy	Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS)	Observations	Study
Low-pressure oxygen plasma	↑ ~25–30% vs untreated	Contact angle ↓ from ~88° to ~67° → ↑ surface energy	IFSS ↑ by ~35%	Plasma treatment enhances surface roughness and bonding without chemicals.	[95]
Organosilane (TEOS, APTES)	↑ ~20% vs raw fiber	Surface energy ↑ from 38 to 54 mJ/m ² (dispersive & polar)	Not directly reported	Enhanced compatibility with hydrophobic matrices.	[96]
Alkali (NaOH), Silane, UV, Plasma	Alkali: ↑ 15–40% Silane: ↑ 20–45%	Contact angle typically ↓ 10–30° depending on treatment	IFSS ↑ up to 50% (varies by matrix)	Alkali and silane are most consistently effective.	[97]
Alkali (NaOH), Silane	Tensile strength ↑ ~22–48% Flexural ↑ ~30%	-	IFSS: Untreated: ~6.2 MPa Alkali: ~8.5 MPa Silane: ~9.6 MPa	One of the earliest quantifications of IFSS for banana-polyester composites.	[98]

Table S11. Performance characteristics of treated banana fibre composites with different polymer matrices in various studies

Surface Treatment	Matrix Type	Mechanical Performance	Thermal Properties	Study
Alkali and hybrid treatments	Various: Polyester, Epoxy, others depending on hybrid system	Tensile strength improved by 30–50%	Improved thermal resistance; stability up to 250–300°C	[100]
Treated and combined with egg shell powder	Epoxy resin	Tensile strength up to 40 MPa, Flexural strength up to 55 MPa	Thermal degradation onset near 275°C	[101]
UV-treated, followed by modification using 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate	Polypropylene	Structural integrity under load	Thermal degradation begins at 295°C	[102]

Alkali and silane treatments	Phenolic resin (Vajram)	20% higher tensile and flexural strength	Enhanced stability post-treatment	[103]
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Table S12. Fibre properties and chemical composition of PALF, taro, and banana fibre at a glance [81, 107, 108]

Properties	Pineapple Fibre	Taro Fibre	Banana Fibre
Density (g/cm ³)	1.52	1.32	1.35
Tensile Strength (MPa)	413	190-300	529
Elongation at Break (%)	1.6	3.47	3.5
Cellulose Content (%)	81	63.85	65.28
Reinforcing Potential	High (rigid, stable)	Low (flexible, weaker)	High (strong, flexible)
Flexibility	Low	High	Moderate

Table S13. Matrix compatibility and interfacial bonding of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites [34, 109, 110]

Parameters	Pineapple Fibre	Taro Fibre	Banana Fibre
Chemical Treatment	5% NaOH	5% NaOH	5% NaOH
Surface Changes After Treatment	Cleaner surface, slight fibrillation	Minor surface changes, limited fibrillation	Significant fibrillation, increased surface roughness
SEM Observations	Improved adhesion, minor interfacial gaps	Poor adhesion, visible pull-out, voids and cavities	Strong bonding, minimal pull-out or voids
Mechanical Interlocking	Moderate	Low	High
Wettability with PP Matrix	Improved, yet slightly uneven	Poor	Excellent
Fibre-Matrix Adhesion Quality	Moderate to Good	Poor	Excellent
Effectiveness of NaOH Treatment	Effective (enhanced bonding with minor gaps)	Less effective (minimal improvement in bonding)	Highly effective (uniform and strong interface)

Note: Higher cellulose content generally improves intrinsic fibre stiffness/strength, but interfacial adhesion depends mainly on surface roughness, fibrillation, cleanliness, and wettability after treatment. Banana fibre shows greater surface fibrillation and wettability improvement after NaOH, which produces stronger mechanical interlocking than PALF.

Table S14. Processing methods and ease of fabrication of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites [18, 80, 105, 111]

Parameters	Pineapple Fibre	Banana Fibre	Taro Fibre
Processing Method	Melt compounding + hot press molding (180 °C)	Melt compounding + hot press molding (180 °C)	Melt compounding + hot press molding (180 °C)
Fibre Behaviour During Mixing	Slight dispersion issues due to stiffness	Excellent dispersion and flexibility during mixing	Poor dispersion; prone to clumping
Thermal Stability	Good	Good	Lower thermal stability
Fiber Breakage Tendency	Moderate (manageable with controlled processing)	Low (fibers remain intact)	High (frequent breakage during melt compounding)
Composite Homogeneity	High (with optimized parameters)	Very high (uniform structure)	Low (irregular structure due to agglomeration and voids)
Ease of Fabrication	Moderate to Good	Excellent	Poor
Final Composite Quality	Consistent (minor dispersion flaws possible)	Highly consistent	Inconsistent (fiber damage and void formation observed)

Table S15: Mechanical and thermal performance of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites [17, 34, 112, 113]

Parameters	Pineapple Fibre Composite	Banana Fibre Composite	Taro Fibre Composite
Tensile Strength	Moderate	Higher	Low
Flexural Strength (MPa)	Moderate	Higher	Low
Elongation at Break (%)	Lower (exact value not given)	Higher (balanced ductility)	Moderate (somewhat improved)
Interfacial Bonding	Moderate to Good	Excellent	Poor
Fiber Dispersion Quality	Good (minor voids)	Excellent	Poor (agglomeration issues)
Onset Degradation Temperature (°C)	Moderate–High (good stability)	High (best thermal stability)	Low (decomposes earlier)
Thermal Stability	Good	Excellent	Poor
Structural Suitability	Medium-duty applications	Suitable for structural applications	Limited to non-structural applications

Table S16. Environmental impact and biodegradability of PALF, taro, and banana fibre composites [7, 81, 114, 115, 116, 117, 118]

Parameters	Pineapple Fibre Composite	Banana Fibre Composite	Taro Fibre Composite
Fibre Source	Agricultural byproduct	Agricultural byproduct	Agricultural byproduct
Waste Valorization Potential	High	High	High
Decomposition Rate	Moderate	Moderate	High (most biodegradable)
End-of-Life Suitability	Compostable with moderate delay	Compostable with moderate delay	Rapid degradation, short life-cycle
Environmental Suitability	Good balance of durability and eco-degradation	Good structural life with eco-end	Best for disposable/eco-packaging use
Sustainability Advantage	Reduces plastic use; moderate lifespan	Reduces plastic use; semi-structural use	High biodegradability; low environmental burden

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